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TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS CREATIVE ACTIVITY THROUGH CIRCLES

Feruza Khusanova

Teacher of the Namangan State Pedagogical Institute, doctor of philosophy (PhD) in the field of pedagogy

E-mail-feruza.khusanova81@mail.com

Annotation: *In this state, there are enlightened methods of effective technological use of TRIZ and ARIZ and the development of creative activities of students through clubs, as well as a portfolio of innovative technologies and basic recommendations of the author.*

Key words: *krujok, tvorcheskaya deyatelnost, nauka, tvorchestvo, iskusstvo, obshchestvo, TRIZ, ARIZ, portfolio.*

ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ ЧЕРЕЗ КРУГИ

Феруза Хусанова

Преподаватель Наманганского государственного педагогического института, доктор философских наук (PhD) в области педагогики

E-mail-feruza.khusanova81@mail.com,

Аннотация: *В данной статье освещены способы эффективного использования технологий ТРИЗ и АРИЗ в развитии творческой активности студентов через клубы, а также портфолио одной из инновационных технологий на основе рекомендации автора показано.*

Ключевые слова: *кружок, творческая деятельность, наука, творчество, искусство, общество, ТРИЗ, АРИЗ, портфолио.*

Introduction: In the period of rapid development of our country in the era of innovative development, it is important to develop the creativity of young people, their creative ideas, to form their knowledge, skills, and qualifications, and at the same time to improve the assessment system based on advanced foreign experiences, international

criteria and requirements, to study international experiences, to comprehensively compare and analyze the existing system, and to cooperate with relevant international and foreign organizations, agencies, and scientific research institutions in a timely manner [2].

It is necessary to effectively use the opportunities of TRIZ and ARIZ editorial staff in developing students' creative activity through circles.

Literature review: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) is a world-renowned method for solving, analyzing, and predicting problems derived from the study of the laws of invention, developed in 1946 by Heinrich Altshuller (1926-1998), and in English this name is usually called the "Theory of Inventive Problem Solving"[4]. The main content of the theory is aimed at identifying ways of creative thinking, and one of the tasks carried out by leading TRIZ practitioners is to develop algorithmic solutions for inventing new systems and improving existing ones. [3].

TRIZ is a problem-solving technique that uses practical methods, tools, databases, and models to develop innovative solutions. It uses systematic analysis and system development models to solve problems.

By 1969, Altshuller had reviewed more than 40,000 patent applications and developed a theory of how innovation occurs, a concept of technical contradictions, a system ideality concept, a matrix of contradictions, and forty principles for developing inventive skills. In later years, he developed the concept of physical contradictions, Suffield analysis (a systematic analysis of the field of matter), standard solutions, laws of evolution of technical systems, and many other theoretical and practical applications [3].

In 1971, Altshuller founded the first TRIZ educational institution, the "Inventions Association", in Baku, Azerbaijan, and managed to establish the first TRIZ laboratory, the "Public Laboratory of Creative Inventions". Altshuller was appointed head of the company's laboratory. Starting in 1986, Altshuller began to focus his research on the development of a consortium for the development of personal creativity from technical TRIZ. In addition, he developed a new version of TRIZ for students of various schools. In 1989, the "TRIZ Association" was established, and Altshuller was elected as its resident. In 1995, the TRIZ Research Institute was established in Boston, USA [3].

Research methodology. The article discusses the technology of increasing the creative activity of students in higher education institutions through clubs based on innovative ideas. Its main structural factors and components are described. The views of a number of scientists on the development of creative activity of students through clubs in higher education are analyzed.

Analysis and Results. TRIZ represents a systematic approach to understanding and defining complex problems: complex problems require scientific solutions, and TRIZ suggests the need to develop a set of strategies and tools to address these scientific solutions. One of the earliest findings of theoretical research is that most problems requiring inventive solutions usually involve the need to resolve a conflict between two conflicting elements. The main goal of TRIZ-based analysis is to develop strategies and tools to address the need for compromise or agreement between two elements.

ARIZ is an algorithmic approach to finding inventive solutions by identifying and resolving contradictions, which employs the “inventive standard solution system” that uses Altshuller’s 40 principles and a matrix of contradictions instead [4]. A number of TRIZ-based computer programs have been developed to assist engineers and inventors in finding inventive solutions to technical problems.

Some of these programs are also designed to use various methods to detect and predict emergency situations and situations that lead to undesirable outcomes. One of the important branches of TRIZ is aimed at analyzing and predicting trends in the development of properties that may develop in existing plants in the future.

The ideal result (IN) is the ideal solution achieved on the basis of the activity. The activity aimed at solving the inventive problem in the form of an ideal result, technical contradiction and physical contradiction is also considered under the concept of “ARIZ”.

The following concepts are used in ARIZ editorial: administrative contradiction - a contradiction between needs and capabilities; technical contradiction - an inverse relationship between the parameters (characteristics) of the technical and technological process; physical contradiction - contradictory [5] physical requirements imposed on the object; separation principle - a method of resolving physical contradictions by separating contradictory requirements; A system (Su-field) is a minimal technical system consisting of two material objects (substances) and a “material”. If the “material” is a source of energy, then one of the substances is a “transmitter”, and the second is a “means”; standard solution is a standard inventive solution of a higher level; laws of development of technical systems; algorithm for solving inventive problems (ARIZ), which combines various specialized TRIZ methods into a single universal tool.

In the last decade, the use of TRIZ tools in German industrial enterprises has been observed, following the principles of new innovative design, and recommends using TRIZ tools selected for identifying customer needs, identifying complex problems and identifying problems, developing and optimizing new concepts at the initial stages of the innovation process. The main aspects of using TRIZ methods are

that they are interesting for all learners, allow them to form knowledge, master creative thinking skills, and develop all types of universal educational activities. They help to solve a problem situation, It encourages students to reflect on the material they have learned, develop creative and logical thinking, and evaluate their own work.

"Young Creators" portfolio. This author's portfolio is used to study educational materials, and its purpose is to require students to understand the essence of the subject, correctly and appropriately indicate the results achieved when mastering the material in group classes. Each student submits to this portfolio the knowledge, skills and competencies acquired from the relevant section of the educational material. (It is also possible to use materials from one educational program) (Figure 1).

This portfolio consists of four parts, each of which includes a set of regulations for student circles, a program called "Young Linguist" for use in this circle, the concept of cultural heritage, and innovative technologies.

Finding effective ways to use existing pedagogical conditions and factors in the development of national character traits in students through works of art, learning to create a methodological framework for teaching literature, and cultivating students' interest in literary works will allow achieving the expected results.

During the course of the group's work, it was determined that the ideas of works of art, as well as the lifestyle, life aspirations, behavior, actions, attitude and behavior of the characters, have the potential to develop in students the willpower qualities inherent in the national character[5].

Conclusion and suggestions: In conclusion, the organization of spiritual and educational events in educational institutions using various forms, methods and means will help students to expand their knowledge of the national character of the Uzbek people, strengthen their existing characteristics, and develop them.

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